

A reusable 3D printed brain-like phantom for benchmarking electrical properties tomography reconstructions

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Funding information

Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO), Grant/Award Number: 18078

Abstract

Purpose: In MR electrical properties tomography (MR-EPT), electrical properties (EPs, conductivity and permittivity) are reconstructed from MR measurements. Phantom measurements are important to characterize the performance of MR-EPT reconstruction methods, since they allow knowledge of reference EPs values. To assess reconstruction methods in a more realistic scenario, it is important to test the methods using phantoms with realistic shapes, internal structures, and dielectric properties. In this work, we present a 3D printing procedure for the creation of realistic brain-like phantoms to benchmark MR-EPT reconstructions.

Methods: We created two brain-like geometries with three different compartments using 3D printing. The first geometry was filled once, while the second geometry was filled three times with different saline-gelatin solutions, resulting in a total of four phantoms with different EPs. The saline solutions were characterized using a probe. 3D MR-EPT reconstructions were performed from MR measurements at 3T. The reconstructed conductivity values were compared to reference values of the saline-gelatin solutions. The measured fields were also compared to simulated fields using the same phantom geometry and electrical properties.

Results: The measured fields were consistent with simulated fields. Reconstructed conductivity values were consistent with the reference (probe) conductivity values. This indicated the suitability of such phantoms for benchmarking MR-EPT reconstructions.

Conclusion: We presented a new workflow to 3D print realistic brain-like phantoms in an easy and affordable way. These phantoms are suitable to benchmark MR-EPT reconstructions, but can also be used for benchmarking other quantitative MR methods.

KEYWORDS

brain models, conductivity, electrical properties tomography, MR phantoms, MR-EPT

1 | INTRODUCTION

MR-based electrical properties tomography (MR-EPT), allows non-invasive characterization of tissue electrical properties (EPs, conductivity σ and relative permittivity ϵ_r) from measurable, RF MRI fields. At MRI frequencies (hundreds MHz), EPs are mostly dependent on the ionic tissue composition. This composition is different between healthy and pathological tissues, making MR-EPT a potential biomarker for tumor diagnosis.^{1,2}

Several methodologies have been developed to reconstruct EPs over the past years.^{1,3} Simulated data are often used to determine the performance (e.g., accuracy/precision) of the developed reconstruction methods, since they allow knowledge of the underlying ground truth EPs values. However, simulations are not a perfect representation of MRI experiments, as for example reconstruction errors arising from imaging artifacts (e.g., B_0 inhomogeneities, Gibbs-ringing) are not present. Therefore, most MR-EPT reconstruction methods presented in literature are also tested on MRI data obtained using phantoms. In contrast to in-vivo, phantoms allow knowledge of reference EPs from independent probe measurements.⁴

MR-EPT reconstructions are frequently tested using simple phantoms (e.g., spheres/cylinders), since the creation of realistic phantoms (geometry, size, and EPs) is often difficult and time consuming.^{5,6} However, the impact of assumptions made in the MR-EPT reconstruction models, which often break down in-vivo, cannot properly be assessed using phantoms with simplified shapes. Additionally, the impact of complex tissue geometries (such as brain gyrifications) on the reconstructions cannot be tested well. Therefore, the use of realistic phantoms is important to test MR-EPT reconstruction methods.

Innovative methods to produce phantoms with realistic geometries have previously been presented. Examples are gel extrusion printing and molding techniques, where brain phantoms were created with realistic relaxation times and electrical properties.⁷⁻¹⁰ However, these methods also present some limitations which affect the assessment of the performance of MR-EPT reconstructions: Gel extrusion printing currently allows creation of phantoms with sizes limited to half of the size of the brain and predefined gel properties.⁷ Hence, new phantoms need to be printed to perform tests with different gel properties. Phantoms constructed using molding techniques are produced in realistic sizes, but they can be fragile and may encounter loss in anatomical detail due to the presence of air pockets.⁸ Also, both approaches suffer from osmotic contamination between layers, which alters the underlying EPs over time.

An alternative method uses 3D printers to extrude interfaces of thick 2D slice phantoms which are then filled

with tissue mimicking gels.¹¹ Yet, the lack of variation in the slice direction is not realistic, limiting correct testing of 3D MR-EPT reconstructions. Also the interfaces are not realistic, although they do limit osmotic processes. To make a structurally anthropomorphic and fully 3D phantom, another approach suggested gluing two half brains together. However, this can result in additional artifacts.¹²

In this work, we developed a new 3D printing method to create 3D, multi-compartment (corresponding to white matter [WM], gray matter [GM], and cerebrospinal fluid [CSF]) phantoms. These compartments can be filled independently with gelatin-based solutions resulting in 3D brain-like phantoms with realistic EPs. This allows benchmarking 3D MR-EPT reconstructions at low cost and preparation times. Here, we focus on conductivity reconstructions, but the same process may be applied for permittivity reconstructions.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Creation of 3D brain models

Four brain-like phantoms with different gelatin-based solutions were created from two different 3D printed brain-like geometries. The two geometries had three compartments each (WM, GM, and CSF), based on: (1) the BigBrain model¹³ with a resolution of 0.4 mm, and (2) one brain model from the BrainWeb database¹⁴ with a resolution of 0.5 mm. These models were processed in several steps, visualized in Figure 1A–D. First, WM, GM, and CSF tissue segmentations were obtained using 3D Slicer (Figure 1B)¹⁵ and smoothed with a median filter (2 mm³ kernel size) to ensure the model is printable in a later stage. Afterward, isolated tissue islands were removed. Additionally, the CSF was dilated 2 mm to ensure that liquids could flow between the GM/CSF plastic surfaces during phantom filling (Figure 1C). Next, 1 mm thick interfaces were created to form plastic shells around the tissue segmentations (Figure 1D). Finally, pipes connected to the different compartments were added to enable phantom filling and cleaning (see arrow in Figure 1G). The surface models were exported as .stl files for 3D printing. The first brain geometry had dimensions 160 × 198 × 150 mm³, respectively in left–right (LR), anterior–posterior (AP), and feet–head (FH) directions. The second brain geometry had dimensions 154 × 189 × 132 mm³.

2.2 | 3D printing

The 3D surface models were printed using an Ultimaker S3 (Ultimaker, Utrecht, The Netherlands), with

FIGURE 1 Flowchart for the creation of the 3D brain phantoms: (A) high resolution brain data, (B) segmented tissues, (C) smoothed and compartmentalized model, (D) surface model, (E) phantom shell being printed, (F) finished printed geometry, (G) filling of the phantom via pipes (orange arrow), and (H) example of cut open phantom with colored gel filling for illustration purposes.

double extruder, where Cura was used to perform slicing and gcode generation of the *.stl* files (Figure 1E,F). One extruder was used to print the brain surfaces using a translucent version of Polyethylene Terephthalate Glycol (PET-G), Makerpoint PET-G Clear, at 250°C ($\sigma = 10^{-10}$ S/m, $\epsilon_r = 3$).¹⁶ The other extruder was used to print support structures of water-soluble Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA), Makerpoint PVA-S, at 225°C. This allowed for the printing of structures with overhangs greater than $\sim 50^\circ$. All layers were printed with a layer height (printing resolution along the z-axis) of 0.15 mm. Finally, the printing bed had a temperature of 85°C to prevent warping and uplift of the print from the build plate during printing. The fabrication of a single brain phantom took approximately 5 days. After printing, the PVA was dissolved in warm water in about a week. To aid the washing process, the PVA support material was printed with a gyroid infill pattern, thus allowing faster water infiltration through the phantom.

2.3 | Brain phantom preparation

The resulting brain geometries were filled with saline-gelatin based solutions to create brain-like phantoms with known EPs (Figure 1G). For this study, the structure with geometry 1 was filled once, while geometry 2 was filled three times to demonstrate the reusability of the phantom, including a filling with homogeneous

properties to compare phantom MRI measurements with simulations (see Section 2.5). An overview of the composition of the phantoms is presented in Table 1. Since we focused on conductivity reconstructions, the conductivity was varied while the permittivity was not changed.

Gelatin was used to prevent flow artifacts in MR images. Salt (NaCl) was used to obtain different conductivity values, which were characterized using probe measurements with an Agilent Technologies 85 070 E dielectric probe at 21°C temperature and 128 MHz. Copper Sulfate (CuSO_4) was used to shorten the T_1/T_2 relaxation times mimicking the relative contrast differences observed between in-vivo WM, GM, and CSF when a single echo spin echo sequence is acquired. Quantitative T_1 and T_2 values for different CuSO_4 /gelatin concentrations were investigated (see Supporting Information S1).

Phantom filling was done when the gelatin-based solution reached $\sim 30^\circ\text{C}$ (viscous gel consistency), to prevent the solutions from leaking through the printed surfaces in the event of printing imperfections. To minimize the presence of air pockets, the phantom was constantly rotated during filling. The phantom preparation took about half a day.

2.4 | MRI experiments

MRI data were acquired with a clinical 3T Ingenia MRI system (Philips Healthcare, Best, The Netherlands) using

TABLE 1 Overview of the saline-gelatin solutions used in the brain models and the corresponding printed geometry.

Brain phantom		NaCl [g/L]	CuSO ₄ [g/L]	Gelatin [g/L]	σ_{ref} [S/m]	$\epsilon_{\text{r,ref}}$ [-]
Phantom 1	WM	3.5	0.5	60	0.68	78
Geometry 1	GM	4.0	0.1	60	0.75	78
	CSF	11.5	0.03	60	1.78	78
Phantom 2	WM	2.2	0.5	60	0.51	78
Geometry 2	GM	3.8	0.1	60	0.73	78
	CSF	13.0	0.05	60	1.99	78
Phantom 3	WM	2.4	0.5	60	0.53	78
Geometry 2	GM	4.2	0.2	60	0.78	78
	CSF	12.2	0.02	60	1.88	78
Phantom 4	WM	2.5	0.3	60	0.55	78
Geometry 2	GM	2.5	0.3	60	0.55	78
	CSF	2.5	0.3	60	0.55	78

Note: Phantom 1–3 are filled with different salt concentrations for WM, GM, and CSF to achieve different conductivity values, while phantom 4 has homogeneous properties. In the last two columns, σ_{ref} and $\epsilon_{\text{r,ref}}$ are respectively the conductivity and relative permittivity measured with the probe (reference values).

Abbreviations: GM, gray matter; WM, white matter.

the body coil in transmit mode and a 15-channel head coil in receive mode, and applying the vendor specific algorithm (Constant Level of Appearance-CLEAR) to convert the receive phase measured with the head coil to the body coil, as if the body coil would have been used for receiving.⁶

Phase images were acquired using three different sequences commonly used in literature for MR-EPT reconstructions: (1) A sagittally oriented 3D balanced steady state free precession (bSSFP) sequence (1 mm isotropic resolution, $\text{FOV} = 224 \times 224 \times 224 \text{ mm}^3$, $T_{\text{R}} = 2.3 \text{ ms}$, $T_{\text{E}} = 1.17 \text{ ms}$, $\text{FA} = 30^\circ$)¹⁷; (2) Two transverse spin echo sequences with opposite readout direction, which were averaged to remove eddy current effects (resolution $2 \times 2 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^3 + 0.5 \text{ mm}$ gap, $\text{FOV} = 224 \times 224 \times 180 \text{ mm}^3$, $T_{\text{R}} = 900 \text{ ms}$, $T_{\text{E}} = 5.2 \text{ ms}$, $\text{FA} = 90^\circ$)¹⁸; (3) A transverse 2D T_2 -weighted turbo spin echo (T_2 TSE) sequence (resolution $1 \times 1 \times 2.5 \text{ mm}^3 + 0.5 \text{ mm}$ gap, $\text{FOV} = 224 \times 224 \times 180 \text{ mm}^3$, $T_{\text{R}} = 4500 \text{ ms}$, $T_{\text{E}} = 80 \text{ ms}$, $\text{FA} = 90^\circ$, Turbo factor = 16).¹⁹ The transceive phase maps (φ^\pm) were then divided by 2 to get the approximated transmit phase used for MR-EPT reconstructions.²⁰ Hereafter, the bSSFP images are shown in axial view for consistency (no post-processing was needed because of the 3D isotropic nature of the bSSFP data).

B_1^+ magnitude ($|B_1^+|$) data were acquired using a 3D actual FA imaging (AFI) (resolution $4 \times 4 \times 3 \text{ mm}^3$,

$\text{FOV} = 256 \times 192 \times 180 \text{ mm}^3$, $T_{\text{R1}} = 50 \text{ ms}$, $T_{\text{R2}} = 250 \text{ ms}$, $T_{\text{E}} = 2.3 \text{ ms}$, $\text{FA} = 65^\circ$).²¹

2.5 | Electromagnetic simulations

To test the usability of these phantoms in MRI measurements, the fields measured using phantom 4 were compared to simulated fields in Sim4Life (ZMT, Zurich Switzerland). The phantom geometry (including the plastic interfaces) was imported in Sim4Life from the .stl file and assigned with the reference (probe) EPs. Inclusion of the plastic interfaces in simulations was important to capture their effect on the simulated fields. The phantom was positioned with respect to the body coil in the same orientation and location as in the measurements using the recorded geometry parameters from MRI measurements as reference.

Complex B_1^+ maps were simulated using a 3T bird-cage coil with two ports at 45° , similar to the clinical coil used in the measurements, as previously reported in literature.²² Quadrature (Tx) and anti-quadrature (Rx) simulations were done to retrieve the transceive phase. Half of this transceive was then used for comparisons with the measurements.¹⁹ B_1^+ magnitude was retrieved from the quadrature simulation.

2.6 | EPT reconstructions and post processing

Helmholtz-based 3D conductivity reconstructions were done to show the possibility of benchmarking MR-EPT reconstruction methods using the developed brain phantoms. For this purpose, conductivity maps were computed from 3D complex B_1^+ data ($|B_1^+|$ from the AFI experiment, and half of the phase from the bSSFP experiment, as this was the only 3D phase mapping sequence used in the measurements) using³:

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\mu_0 \omega} \text{Im} \left\{ \frac{\nabla^2 B_1^+}{B_1^+} \right\} \quad (1)$$

with, μ_0 is the vacuum permeability and ω the Larmor frequency. The $|B_1^+|$ was interpolated to the same 1 mm^3 isotropic grid as the bSSFP using cubic interpolation.

Conductivity was reconstructed with a 5 point Laplacian kernel to reduce noise effects.²³ To evaluate the reconstructed conductivity, a segmentation was then created using the magnitude weighted images. The reconstructed conductivity maps were only evaluated on eroded tissue segmentation masks to exclude boundary artifacts. These eroded masks were obtained by excluding the outer

voxels from the initial tissue masks. Here, voxels were eroded if the 5 point derivative kernel included voxels outside the initial tissue masks.

Finally, a median filter ($21 \times 21 \times 21$ voxels) was applied as previously suggested in literature.² Only voxels belonging to the eroded mask of the same compartment as the central voxel of the kernel were included in the filter. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were computed within the eroded masks.

3 | RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the acquired MRI data using the four brain-like phantoms. The signal magnitude images of the bSSFP, T₂TSE, and SE experiments clearly show the structure of the brain phantoms and the signal drop at tissue interfaces due to the plastic surfaces. For the T₂TSE and SE images, a clear contrast difference between the different compartments can be seen for phantom 1–3, as expected from the phantom preparations. Geometric differences between phantom 2–4 are due to a different angulation of the phantom in the scanner. The bSSFP transceive phase and AFI B₁⁺ magnitude, used for EPT reconstructions, are shown in the fourth and fifth column, respectively.

The |B₁⁺| maps are comparable overall, however, for phantoms 1–3 these maps are affected by oversaturation in the CSF/ventricles, which may be caused by imperfect spoiling causing biases for tissues with different T₁/T₂ (different concentration of CuSO₄). Consequently, this effect is not visible in a case with similar relaxation times in all tissues (phantom 4).²⁴

Figure 3 shows a comparison between the measurements of homogeneous phantom 4 and its digital twin for a center slice of the phantom. The simulated ϕ^{\pm} and |B₁⁺| fields match the measured fields as indicated by the low relative errors (up to 10% at the edges). This shows the validity of the measurements with this novel 3D printed phantom. Causes of such small differences may be the little mismatch in the phantom placement between measurements and simulations and the sensitivity of the B₁ mapping method to imaging imperfections which are not present in simulations, for example, B₀ inhomogeneities.

Figure 4 shows conductivity reconstructions for the 4 brain phantoms before and after erosion. The reference conductivity values from probe measurements are used here to generate the reference conductivity maps.

The computed tissue conductivity values using all the voxels in the brain masks after erosion, displayed as a box-plot in the last column, match the reference conductivity values (dashed lines) from phantom construction for most

FIGURE 2 Results from MRI experiments for the four phantoms. Gray scale images show signal magnitude from balanced SSFP (bSSFP), T₂-weighted turbo spin echo (T₂TSE), and SE MRI acquisitions. The fourth column shows the transceive phase (ϕ^{\pm}) as acquired with the 3D bSSFP. The last column shows the B₁⁺ magnitude acquired with the 3D actual flip angle imaging (AFI).

FIGURE 3 Comparison between measured and simulated ϕ^\pm (top) and $|B_1^+|$ (bottom) for phantom 4. The white voxels in the measured and simulated fields were drawn in post-processing and were created respectively from the segmentation and simulated ground truth conductivity to evaluate possible phantom placement mismatch. On the right column the fields along center line in left-right (LR) and anterior-posterior (AP) directions are compared. The dashed line represents the measurements, while the solid line represents the simulated data.

FIGURE 4 Electrical properties tomography (EPT) reconstructions for four brain phantoms. Reference conductivity maps (first column) were obtained by assigning reference conductivity values to the three different tissues (white matter [WM], gray matter [GM], and CSF). Conductivity reconstructions are shown in the second and third column, where the third column only displays reconstructed voxels within the eroded mask, used to generate the boxplots (fourth column). The dashed lines in the boxplot indicate the reference conductivity values.

tissues. A clear decrease in reconstruction accuracy can be observed for the CSF regions, especially of geometry 1. For these regions, only a small amount of reconstructed voxels are present in the eroded mask, which leads to underestimations with the filtered 3D Helmholtz reconstruction.

Furthermore, for the homogeneous phantom the reconstructed mean conductivity is the same for the three different compartments, as expected from phantom construction. Yet, the mean values show an overestimation by 10% compared to the reference value which may originate from temperature differences between phantom preparation and scanning.²⁵ The exact temperature of the phantom was not be measured before MRI measurements since this would have compromised the structural integrity of the gel.

Finally, conductivity reconstructions show typical transceive phase errors at the edges of the phantoms as observed in literature.²⁰ These errors are visible thanks to the realistic size/shape of the developed phantoms. Two other examples of conductivity reconstructions on phantom 3 using different reconstruction methods are presented in the Supporting Information S2.

4 | DISCUSSION

In this work, we presented an approach that uses 3D printing to create realistically shaped brain phantoms to benchmark the performances of MR-EPT reconstruction methods. We demonstrated the creation of 3D brain-like structures by producing four brain phantoms with different geometries and properties. The phantoms were filled using saline-gelatin solutions, and could easily be washed and refilled. This allowed for the creation of multiple phantoms with different EPs in a cost- and time-effective manner.

Applicability of the phantom for MR-EPT reconstructions was demonstrated by the good agreement between the reconstructed conductivity values from MRI measurements (within eroded tissue masks) and probe measurements. Outside the masks, the reconstructions are influenced by the well-known boundary artifacts.²⁶ The validity of the phantom was furthermore demonstrated by the good agreement between the measured and simulated fields using the homogeneous phantom.

In literature, other studies have similarly investigated the possibility of creating anthropomorphic brain phantoms using 3D printing methods. There are however several issues with the presented methods that may limit applications of these phantoms for the characterization of MR-EPT reconstruction methods. One issue is the osmotic process between tissues that are in direct contact leading to alterations of EPs, as present in molding and extruded gel

printing phantoms.^{7,8} This makes the comparison between the reconstructed conductivity values and the reference values from phantom preparation difficult.²⁷ Alternatively, in phantoms with 3D printed tissue interfaces, which prevent ionic diffusion, geometric variations in the slice direction are not present, limiting the use of these phantoms to the characterization of 2D EPT reconstruction methods.¹¹ Another issue is the possibility to reuse these phantoms. This is important as all gel based phantoms degrade over time by evaporation/sublimation if not stored fully airtight.⁹ Additionally, reuse can be beneficial to create multiple phantoms with the same geometry but different properties. The latter approach allows easy reuse because of the straight-forward preparation, while reuse in molding and gel extrusion printing approaches is more difficult due to longer fabrication times.⁷

Building upon the strengths of prior methods, we made several design choices. First, to achieve realistic 3D brain sizes and complex tissue shapes mimicking brain gyrifications, plastic interfaces were printed with the help of a water-soluble support material. Realistic brain sizes and shapes are necessary to properly test the impact of approximations (e.g., the transceive phase approximation) in conductivity reconstructions. They can also allow investigating the trade-off between the necessary imaging resolution/SNR/scan time for accurate brain MR-EPT reconstructions.²⁷ These effects cannot be tested in phantoms with simple geometries. Second, as aforementioned, tissue interfaces also prevent osmosis between structures with different ionic content, which would otherwise lead to uncontrolled electrical properties over time.²⁷ Finally, by using gelatin, the phantoms are easily reusable as they allow washing and refilling, thus minimizing the production time. We believe these aspects make the proposed phantoms an important step forward in MR-EPT phantoms fabrication.

There are also some limitations to our work. First, the use of plastic interfaces between tissues leads to signal losses in the corresponding voxels. Additionally, these interfaces locally affect (only at the interfaces) the B_1^+ field if compared to B_1^+ fields measured/simulated without interfaces. Both aspects lead to additional numerical errors at tissue interfaces in MR-EPT reconstructions to the already existing numerical errors caused by the derivative calculations.^{6,26} Yet, this is not an issue when reconstructions are evaluated in homogeneous regions,²⁸ since in these regions the curvature of the B_1^+ field (proportional to the electrical properties) is not affected by plastic interfaces. This is here confirmed by the good agreement between the reconstructed and the reference conductivity values, demonstrating the suitability of such phantoms for benchmarking MR-EPT reconstructions. Consequently, we concluded that the choice of using plastic

interfaces is a good trade-off between the prevention of osmotic processes and the numerical reconstruction errors at tissue interfaces, which are always present in MR-EPT reconstructions as shown by the EPT Challenge results.²⁹ Second, air pockets may arise in some gyrifications during phantom filling due to the complex 3D morphology of these phantoms. To minimize this issue, the phantoms were tilted in different directions, allowing air to move out of the phantom during filling. In the future, this may be further prevented by redesigning the location of the filling pipes. Third, the lifetime of these phantoms is limited to a few weeks. Since the phantoms are not completely airtight, they slowly dry out. Yet, this is not a major problem, since the phantom can easily be cleaned and refilled. Finally, we did not alter the permittivity values as we focused on conductivity reconstructions. Similarly, other phantoms may be created to study permittivity reconstructions by varying permittivity using glucose or ethanol.^{27,30}

Ultimately, these phantoms offer a versatile platform for testing a wide range of MR-EPT reconstruction methods. To this end, this phantom is used in the MR-EPT reconstruction challenge.³¹ Furthermore, these phantoms may be particularly suitable for testing the accuracy and generalizability of DL based methods, because of the brain-like geometry and the reusability with known, variable EPs. Finally, these phantoms may also be used in applications outside of MR-EPT, for example, benchmarking other quantitative MRI methods.

5 | CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a new workflow for the creation of realistic 3D printed brain phantoms. We demonstrated the feasibility and suitability of the proposed fabrication technique for the characterization of the performance of MR-EPT reconstructions. The proposed technique enables the creation of 3D brain phantoms realistic in shape and size, with minimal cost and complexity (e.g., preparation time). The ease of production, using conventional 3D printers, makes the phantoms readily adoptable by other centers and suitable for repeated use.

In addition to the characterization of MR-EPT reconstruction methods, the phantom may also be used for other quantitative MRI methods.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We thank Dr. E. Versteeg, Dr. O. van der Heide, and F. Xu for performing the T_1 , T_2 measurements. This work has been financed by the Netherlands Organization for Scientific Research (NWO), VENI grant number: 18078. We acknowledge the contribution for this research by

the Artificial Intelligence working group of the EWUU alliance.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

The data created in this study are available in ADEPT, which can be accessed from: <https://doi.org/10.34894/V0HBJ8>.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website.

Supporting Information S1. T_1/T_2 measurements of CuSO_4 -gelatin mixtures.

Figure S1. Quantitative T_1 (left) and T_2 (right) values for the 15 vials with different CuSO_4 gelatin concentrations.

Table S1. Quantitative T_1 and T_2 values for different concentrations of CuSO_4 and gelatin.

Supporting Information S2. Comparing several conductivity reconstruction methods on a brain phantom.

Figure S2. Conductivity reconstructions using different reconstruction methods. The boxplots were computed using the reconstructed conductivity values within the eroded tissue mask on the displayed slice. "P" (second column) indicates reconstructions using only the transceive phase.

How to cite this article: Meerbothe TG, Florczak S, van den Berg CAT, Levato R, Mandija S. A reusable 3D printed brain-like phantom for benchmarking electrical properties tomography reconstructions. *Magn Reson Med*. 2024;1-9. doi: 10.1002/mrm.30189